

Use of precision irrigation for water efficient management in a processing tomato commercial farm

S. Millán¹, C. Montesinos¹, J.M. Esteban², J. Casadesus³, C Campillo¹.

¹Centre for Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura (CICYTEX), Department of Horticulture, Finca La Orden, Regional Government of Extremadura, Highway A-V, Km 372, 06187 Guadajira, Badajoz, Spain.

²Plant sustainability Manager (Agraz), Ctra. N-V km 390, 06195 Villafranco del Guadiana, Badajoz, Spain

³Program of Efficient Use of Water in Agriculture, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), Parc de Gardeny (PCiTAL), Fruitcentre, 25003 Lleida, Spain

Abstract

Abstract

Nowadays, the incorporation of new technologies in the agricultural sector has made it possible to carry out precision automatic irrigation, allowing farmers to make more efficient irrigation decisions, increasing yields, and preserving water resources. The objective of this study was to validate the IrriDesk tool under real field conditions. Our goal is to install an automated drip irrigation system in a processing tomato field in "Vegas Bajas del Guadiana" and assess how IrriDesk can achieve profitable yields while limiting water consumption to less than 5000 m³/ha. The study was carried out during the 2023 season as part of the DIGISPAC project in collaboration with the companies UNILEVER and GRUPO CONESA through their company AGRAZ in commercial farm of processing tomato variety 'UG-16112' located in Talavera la Real (Extremadura, Spain) belonging to the company Explotaciones Aldea del Conde, S. L. (Alconsa S.L.). A map of apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) was elaborated to characterize the spatial variability of the plot and to select the points where the sensors that were part of the decision-making process of the automatic irrigation system were to be installed. The plot was divided into two zones: one zone irrigation was managed by the farmer and the other zone irrigation was carried out automatically with the IrriDesk web platform. The amount of water applied in the farmer's zone (613mm) was higher than that in the IrriDesk zone (467mm), which applied 26% less water than the farmer. The water applied was lower than the maximum water limit set at the beginning of the campaign (500 mm). In relation to production, it is observed that there are no differences in the production obtained in the two zones: 148T/ha in farmer and 140T/ha in IrriDesk. About the quality parameter °Brix, which is very important for the industry and to be considered when establishing the economic yields of the crop, it was observed that the highest values of °Brix were obtained in the IrriDesk area (5.15 to 5.45).

Keywords: apparent electrical conductivity; water use efficiency; Irridesk; sensors, digital twins, Soil moisture sensors, automatic irrigation systems, regulated deficit irrigation.

INTRODUCTION

The world is facing increased pressure on its water resources due to population growth, climate change, and intensified agriculture. The UN World Water Development Report 2020 (Water,2020), states that 69% of water withdrawals are used for agricultural purposes. With declining rainfall and rising temperatures, there is a reduction in available water resources, leading to a growing reliance on irrigation for crop water supply. As a result, there is a need to focus on using irrigation water more efficiently. Farmers are adopting new technologies that enable localized and controlled supply of irrigation water.

Incorporating new technologies for irrigation applications is crucial because localized irrigation can significantly increase efficiency, achieving yields of up to 95% compared to the 30-40% yields of traditional gravity irrigation systems. This efficiency is further enhanced by proper irrigation management, which involves defining the irrigation strategy through correct programming. A new approach, known as 'Precision Irrigation' (PI), involves designing irrigation systems to provide different treatments based on the spatial variability of the plots, temporal requirements in each management zone, and the availability of water and energy resources.

Precision irrigation involves managing irrigation water in such a way that water is applied in a specific location, at the right time, and in the right amount to achieve the highest crop production. This is not tied to a particular technology, but rather involves systematically collecting data on the crop, climate, and field. Technology models the soil-water-plant-climate system and uses automatic control techniques to achieve optimal and efficient production. According to Fuentes et al. (2020), precision irrigation in agriculture will help mitigate the effects of climate change and improve the profitability of farms by adjusting irrigation systems to meet the actual water needs of crops.

IrriDesk is a modern digital tool that utilizes advanced crop monitoring technologies and simulation to ensure precise irrigation. It operates based on an algorithm that integrates data from meteorology, remote sensing, and sensors installed on the fields. IrriDesk can function automatically, starting from data collection in the field, through processing and assimilation into a digital twin, to decision-making and transmission to the irrigation system controller. This tool has been tested in various crops such as plum trees (Millán et al., 2019), apple trees (Domínguez-Niño et al., 2019), and hedgerow olive trees (Millán et al., 2020), resulting in a 15% improvement in water productivity compared to human expert management and an 80% reduction in the time required for irrigation monitoring and control. IrriDesk (<https://irridesk.ddns.net/>) is available through different commercial platforms, enabling connection with sensors and irrigation controllers. Additionally, it is useful in managing irrigation when water allocations are limited (deficit irrigation). IrriDesk is available through different commercial platforms, enabling connection with sensors and irrigation controllers.

The objective of this study was to validate the IrriDesk tool under real field conditions. Our goal is to install an automated drip irrigation system in a processing tomato field in "Vegas Bajas del Guadiana" and assess how IrriDesk can achieve profitable yields while limiting water consumption to less than 5000 m³/ha. This research is vital for the future of tomato farming, and we believe it will make a significant contribution to the industry's water conservation efforts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The work was carried out within the DIGISPAC project, in collaboration with the companies UNILEVER and GRUPO CONESA through their company AGRAZ in a commercial plot of processing tomato of 15 hectares belonging to the company Explotaciones Aldea del Conde, S. L. (Alconsa S.L.), in the municipality of Talavera la Real, Badajoz, Spain (latitude 38°84'65.64 "N, longitude 6°72'59.18 "W, datum WGS84).

The plot has an area of 9.46 ha of processing tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) variety UG16112, transplanted between 3 and 10 April 2023. The planting density was 29,000 plants/a, double row and staggered, with a distance between continuous plants of 46 cm.

The plot was divided into two sectors with differential irrigation management and drip irrigation system, following the following criteria (Figure 1c):

- CICYTEX (IrriDesK): automatic irrigation management following the information provided by the IrriDesK web platform. This tool allows controlled deficit irrigation (CDI) strategies that consist of imposing water deficits in the phenological stages that are less sensitive to water stress to reduce vegetative growth while minimally affecting yield and fruit quality. For this study, RDC was applied at the ripening stage. The area was 5.12 ha.
- AGRAZ (Farmer): irrigation management traditionally carried out by the farmer. The zone had an area of 4.34 ha.

Before transplanting the crop, the plot was spatially characterised using historical maps of the Normalised Vegetation Index (NDVI) (figure 1a) and massive measurements of the apparent soil conductivity (Eca) with the Dualem-1S sensor made by the GREENFIELD company (figure 1b). The vegetation map (NDVI) of the previous season allows us to identify areas of differential development in the plot, which in most cases is due to differences in soil texture. In the case of ECA measurement, it is a parameter also related to soil water content and texture. Low values indicate a higher sand content and higher clay content. Although the differences in this case were small in the plot, no major differences in soil textures were identified. Both measurements show different soil distributions in the plot, with the southern zone having a higher water retention capacity than the northern zone. However, this greater capacity caused a more significant development in the crop observed with lower NDVI values, probably due to excessive water with production losses due to waterlogging.

The study of the spatial variability within a plot is essential to identify the control points to install the sensors to adjust the irrigation schedules to the soil differences existing in this plot. Based on the information obtained, three clearly differentiated zones were identified in each of the sectors from north to south.

In IrriDesK three control points and two in farmer were selected (figure 1b). In these points soil water content was monitored with Teros 10 capacitance probes (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, USA). To characterise the wet bulb in the dripper's influence environment, nine sensors were placed 20 cm deep and 10 cm apart from the dripper horizontally towards the bed. The moisture sensors allow irrigation to be adjusted to the real water needs of the crop at each phenological stage, enabling the model to make changes in the established irrigation doses according to the availability of water in the soil.

Figure 1: Test plot: a) Normalised Vegetation Index Map, b) Soil apparent electrical conductivity map, c) Zones with different irrigation management (CICYTEX) with Irridesk system management and AGRAZ farmer management.

Irrigation volumes were recorded daily using digital water meters (MTKD-M, Zenner, Villaviciosa de Odón, Madrid) installed in each irrigation zone. In addition, an Apogee SI411 thermal sensor (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, USA) was installed at each control point. At the same time, three monitoring points were selected where punctual measurements of crop water status (leaf water potential) were taken with a PUMP-UP (PMS instruments) portable pressure camera. All the control and monitoring points were used to obtain the commercial production, selecting a surface of 9m² in each of the points.

In the IrriDesK web platform (<https://irridesk.ddns.net/>), the user must perform a series of tasks: describe the plot, configure the sensors, and define the irrigation strategy to be followed in the irrigation campaign. Once this has been done, the system is autonomous, it is only necessary to supervise its correct operation and if a system failure occurs, it informs the user by means of alarms. IrriDesK collects data from sensors in the field (figure 1b), downloading it on demand and at regular intervals throughout the day to ensure a reliable dataset for analysis. The system then analyzes the data and calculates the volumes of water needed for irrigation. Once a day, IrriDesK uses the information from moisture sensors and user-defined irrigation limits to determine the irrigation rate. This is done using an algorithm that combines an estimation of crop water requirements based on the water balance with adjustments based on sensor readings.

In terms of irrigation scheduling, IrriDesK sends the updated irrigation rates to the datalogger, which then activates the necessary equipment (such as solenoid valves or pumps) to apply the required irrigation rates.

One of the most important information to be introduced in the system is the irrigation strategy to be followed. This information is included in the campaign plan where the distribution of water during the campaign is established. In this case, the values entered in IrriDesK were imposed by the farmer, who indicated that 550 mm were to be applied during the whole irrigation campaign. Maximum limit of 650 mm and a lower limit of 400 mm were entered in IrriDesK (Figure 2). These limits establish the range within which irrigation allocations must be maintained so the system can adjust irrigation according to specific conditions. The system adjust irrigation scheduling according to the specific conditions of each field control point (soil moisture sensors). In this case, a deficit irrigation strategy was added at the time of fruit ripening, establishing recommendations for deficit irrigation use by campillo et al, (2022).

Figure 2. Maximum (max) and minimum (min) accumulated water values initially set initially established.

Setting the desired maximum and minimum limits allows the system to adjust irrigation to the specific conditions of each zone in the field. In addition, for greater adjustment, the system allows the limits to be closer in more critical phenological moments such as vegetative development and flowering in processing tomatoes (week 9 to 12) and allows the system

greater freedom in making decisions in less critical periods such as ripening (from week 14 onwards), when it is possible to save water without losing production.

Prior to harvesting, 12 points were selected in each area according to the spatial variability existing in these areas. Harvesting took place on 25/07/2023 when there were more than 85% of red fruits. At each point, 24 bushes were collected in 9 m² and the tomatoes were classified into red (commercial production), green and overripe (non-commercial production). From each point, 30 red tomatoes were randomly selected to determine the sugar content (°Brix) using a refractometer (Mettler-Toledo, model RE40D).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In processing tomato cultivation there are the following crop phases: transplanting phase (Phase I), rapid growth phase (Phase II), fruit growth phase (Phase III) and ripening phase (Phase IV). It is observed that after transplanting (Phase I), IrriDesK applies less water than that imposed in the seasonal plan. At the time of transplanting, the soil profile is filled with water up to the maximum depth that reaches the roots, so that IrriDesK adjusts to the specific conditions of the plot and reduces the water applied in this phase. In the rapid growth phase (phase II) RDC cannot be applied as a water deficit in this period can lead to a high number of flower abortion. So, here the system follows the previously imposed seasonal plan. Then, in the fruit growth phase (phase III), RDC strategies cannot be applied either, as fruit fattening must be encouraged. IrriDesK is modulated and adjusted to the seasonal plan initially foreseen in the campaign so that the crop does not suffer water stress. In the ripening phase of the crop (IV), the green fruits start to turn red, and this is a favourable period to apply RDC strategies (figure 3a). IrriDesK adjusts at this stage of the crop by reducing the amount of water applied to the crop. The adjustments made by the IrriDesk model during the crop cycle, based on the campaign programming and the measurements of water content in the soil and crop water status made at the different control points, made it possible to reduce the volumes of water applied in relation to the traditional irrigation carried out by the farmer, while remaining within the maximum limits of 500 mm established for the irrigation campaign.

In figure 3b shows the amount of water applied in each of the management zones during the 2023 irrigation season, Farmer(559mm) and IrriDesk (413mm). The greatest water differentiation occurred at the end of the crop cycle where the system began to adjust irrigation as it was considered an area where production could be maintained and brix could be improved.

Figure 3. a) Adjusting IrriDesk to the seasonal plan. b) Amount of water applied in each of the management zones during the 2023 irrigation season, Farmer (559mm) and IrriDesk (413mm).

The amount of water applied in the farmer's zone was higher than that in the IrriDesK zone, which applied 26% less water than the farmer. The water applied was lower than the maximum water limit set at the beginning of the campaign (500 mm).

In relation to production, it is observed that there are no differences in the production obtained in the two zones (table 1). About the quality parameter °Brix, which is very important for the industry and to be considered when establishing the economic yields of the crop, it was observed that the highest values of °Brix were obtained in the IrriDesk area. These differences in brix allow a better value of euros/T in the industry, which improves the profit results by compensating the minimum drop in production with the increase in quality and a reduction of the water applied. It is essential in years when, due to drought, the maximum water to be used by the crop is limited to 5000 m³/ha and the farmer must manage irrigation as efficiently as possible.

Table 1. Water applied, rainfall, total water applied, total tomato yield and quality parameter (°Brix)

Zones	Applied water (mm)	Precipitation (mm)	Total (mm)	Production (t/ha)	° Brix
Farmer	559	54	613	148.59	5.15
IrriDesK	413	54	467	140.06	5.42*

The asterisk indicates differences between treatments $p < 0.05$ according to the Tukey test.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a precision automatic irrigation system was tested in a commercial industrial tomato plot, carried out using the IrriDesK web platform, comparing it with the irrigation management carried out by a farmer.

- IrriDesk helps the farmer to adapt controlled deficit irrigation strategies in tomato cultivation in situations of low water availability and to improve crop quality.
- IrriDesk permit to the farmer takes the reins of irrigation management. This technology enables automatic irrigation based on the agronomic management selected by the farmer, adjusting the water doses according to the soil moisture conditions.
- IrriDesk is a water-saving champion, using a significantly lower volume of water than the farmer (around 26% on average). It does this by adapting to the information provided by the sensors in each area.
- IrriDesk makes it possible to maintain good production with a water limit set as an initial target.
- IrriDesk can adjust irrigation scheduling according to the water content of the soil and improve water use efficiency.
- IrriDesk can improve the quality of processing tomatoes and, consequently, the profitability of the crop.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Unilever and Agraz, part of the Conesa group, for their commitment to more sustainable and environmentally friendly agriculture. To Antonio Tienza and the company Explotaciones Aldea del Conde, S.L. (Alconsa S.L.), for allowing the study to be carried out on their plot.

DigiSPAC (TED2021-131237B-C22) projects funded by the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities/State Research Agency/10.13039/ 501100011033 co-financed by ERDF a

way of making Europe and by EU Next Generation/Spanish Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan

Literature cited

- Campillo, C., Márquez, E., Muñoz, P., Dorado, T., Sánchez-Porro, A. and González, V. (2022). Effects of regulated deficit irrigation on total soluble solids evolution in processing tomato. *Acta Hort.* 1351, 13-18 DOI: 10.17660/ActaHortic.2022.1351.3
- Capraro Fuentes, F. A., & Tosetti Sanz, S. R. (2020). Herramientas modernas de gestión en riego de precisión basadas en dispositivos electrónicos, programas informáticos y técnicas de control automático.
- Casadesús, J., Mata, M., Marsal, J., and Girona, J. (2012). A general algorithm for automated scheduling of drip irrigation in tree crops. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 83, 11-20.
- Hídricos, R. (2020). *Agua y Cambio climático*.
- Domínguez-Niño, J. M., Oliver-Manera, J., Girona, J., and Casadesús, J. (2020). Differential irrigation scheduling by an automated algorithm of water balance tuned by capacitance- type soil moisture sensors. *Agricultural Water Management*, 228, 105880.
- Millán, S., Campillo, C., Casadesús, J., Moñino, M. J., Vivas, A., & Prieto, M. H. (2019). Automated irrigation scheduling for drip-irrigated plum trees. In *Precision agriculture'19* (pp. 59-66). Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Millán, S., Campillo, C., Casadesús, J., Pérez-Rodríguez, J. M., and Prieto, M. H. (2020). Automatic Irrigation Scheduling on a Hedgerow Olive Orchard Using an Algorithm of Water Balance Readjusted with Soil Moisture Sensors. *Sensors*, 20(9), 2526.
- Millán, S., Campillo, C. & Montesinos, C. (2023). Reg de precisió en una parcel·la comercial de fruiters. *Dossier tècnic*, (121), 18-21.